

Abbreviations

ALI: acute limb ischemia

APTT: activated partial thromboplastin time

BA: brachial artery

CDT: catheter-directed thrombolysis

FA: femoral artery

LTT: local thrombolytic therapy

MAE: major adverse event

MT: mechanical thrombectomy

PMT: percutaneous mechanical thrombectomy

PTA: percutaneous transluminal angioplasty

RA: radial artery

STILE: Surgery or Thrombolysis in Lower Extremity Ischemia

TB: transbrachial

TF: transfemoral

TOPAS: Thrombolysis Or Peripheral Artery Surgery

tPA: tissue plasminogen activator

TR: transradial